

Application of Artificial Neural Network for Efficient Earthquake Resistant Design of Building: A Study

Bikash Behera¹ and Alope Kumar Datta²

^{1,2} National Institute of Technology Durgapur, India.

Abstract This research paper presents the development and implementation of an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) model for the design of efficient earthquake-resistant reinforced concrete buildings. With the increasing frequency and severity of seismic events worldwide, it is imperative to enhance the seismic performance of structures to ensure the safety of occupants and the preservation of property. Traditional design methods often rely on simplified assumptions and empirical equations, which may not fully capture the complexities of seismic behavior. By utilizing a comprehensive dataset of structural designs, EQ records and performance evaluations, the ANN model has been trained to generate efficient and EQ resilient structural designs while meeting safety standards. In this paper, for development of ANN model huge data required such as input and output data, for input data various earthquake ground motion (EQGM) data are considered here and structural design parameter collected from Finite Element Software (ETABS) as output data. Using ETABS 3-D 2 Story RC frame building is designed and Time History Analysis has been performed using different EQ ground motion data. Training of ANN model has been done using INPUT data such as PGA, PGV, PGD, and Time duration of EQGM and design parameter of RC building as OUTPUT data such as Maximum Displacement, Story drift, Base shear, Overturning moment. After getting a robust ANN model the same model can be used for different seismic zone to predict the design parameter of RC structure for new EQGM data efficiently. Prediction of design parameter from ANN model for new EQGM can be compared with the design parameter of RC building from ETABS. Therefore, efficient earthquake resistant design and safety of RC building can be ensured in different seismic zone with less computational effort. The developed model works fine and the procedure adopted here promises future application and research.

Keywords RC structure, Non-linear dynamic analysis (ETABS), Artificial Neural Network (MATLAB).

Introduction

One of the most important areas of civil engineering research for a long time has been the study of earthquake-resistant building design. Since earthquakes are occurring more frequently across the globe, it is crucial to design structures that can resist these kinds of natural calamities. This study explores the use of Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) as a powerful tool for improving and optimizing earthquake-resistant building design efficiency. Seismic-resistant design techniques have historically relied on empirical data and intricate mathematical models to forecast how a structure will behave during an earthquake. But the application of artificial neural networks offers a viable way to transform this industry. Inspired by the neural network of the human brain, artificial neural networks, or ANNs, have remarkable computational powers, especially in pattern recognition, learning, and prediction. For earthquake resistant design of building, we may follow Indian Standard code, for that we have to go for analytical problem and it will take much time. There are different Finite Element Software for the earthquake resistant design of building viz. ETABS, STAAD Pro and many more. If we go for Finite Element software huge computational effort required and expertise as well. To overcome this problem like time consumption and huge computational effort, we can go for different AI model such as ANN (Artificial Neural Network). Recently, researcher have used ANN model in different sector of civil engineering. Calleda et al. [1] used neural network inversion for the Optimal Design of Earthquake-Resistant Buildings. This paper proposes a procedure to cost-effectively design earthquake-resistant buildings, which is based on the inversion of an artificial neural network and on an optimization algorithm for the minimum total cost under building code constraints. Tsompanakis et al. [2] used artificial neural network for Simulating the seismic response of embankments. The simulation of the seismic response of a typical embankment is the main application of ANNs in their work. The finite-element method is used to assess the dynamic response of the embankment, where an equivalent-linear procedure can account for the nonlinear behaviour of the geo-materials. In this study, properly trained artificial neural networks (ANNs) take the place of this incredibly laborious process. Möller et al. [3] used neural networks for Structural optimization for performance-based design in earthquake engineering. Their study addresses an approach to performance-based design in the context of earthquake engineering. The objective is the optimization of the total structural cost, under constraints related to minimum target reliabilities specified for the different limit states or performance requirements. Conte et al. [4] developed Seismic Response Modelling of Multi-Story Buildings Using Neural Networks. Gholizadeh and Salajegheh [5] used a modified firefly algorithm and a new neural network for the Performance-based optimum seismic design of steel structures. Jafarzadeh et al. [6] They used ANN model for Predicting Seismic Retrofit Construction Cost. Their study demonstrated predicting retrofit construction cost by employing a more advanced modelling technique, known as the artificial neural network (ANN) methodology. Using this methodology, a series of non-parametric ANN models was developed based on significant predictors of the retrofit net construction cost (RNCC). Arslan [7] used neural networks in his paper for effective design parameters on earthquake performance of RC buildings. Alvanitopoulos et al. [8] used Neuro-fuzzy

techniques for the classification of earthquake damages in buildings. Nguyen et al. [9] used artificial neural network and extreme gradient boosting for Prediction of seismic drift responses of planar steel moment frames. Lautour et al. [10] used artificial neural networks for artificial neural networks. Hait et al. [11] used artificial neural network for Prediction of global damage index of reinforced concrete building. Hansapinyo et al. [12] used AI system for Seismic Building Damage Prediction From GIS-Based Building Data. From the literature review, it has been found that development of artificial neural network model for efficient earthquake resistant design of building needs special attention in research. In this study an attempt has been made to obtain robust artificial neural network model to predict the design parameter of earthquake resistant building efficiently and accurately. The Study has been conducted by using for modelling and data generation of two story 3-D RC frame structure using real type EQGM. Then the ANN model has developed in MATLAB software utilizing generated data for a typical building to demonstrate the efficacy and simplicities of the proposed model. Two software are used one is finite element software (ETABS 2020) for modelling of 2-story 3-D frame structure and also for Non-linear dynamic analysis. Another software is MATLAB 2021a for the development of artificial neural network (ANN) model.

Data Generation

For development of ANN model huge data is required such as input and output data. Peak values of EQGM data viz. PGA, PGV, PGD and time duration considered for input data and structural design parameter are considered as output data for ANN training and modelling. In this study, EQGM data are collected from PEER ground motion database [13]. 3-D 2 Story RC frame building taken from the work done by authors B. D. N. Deo and A. K. Datta (Vol. 2) Page-193, Reference [14].

Building Data

3-D 2 Story RC frame building having 7m total height (bottom story 4m and top story 3m). Beam size 400*500mm, column size 500*500mm, M25 grade concrete and steel Fe415 grade. Using ETABS 2020 version [15] the modelled frame structure is shown in Fig. 1. And also, for input data EQGM shown in Fig. 2. that figure taken from ETABS like that 25 EQGM data considered in this study.

Fig. 1. The above figures a, b, and c shows the 2 story 3-D frame structure plan view, structure without Non-linear dynamic analysis and structure after Non-linear dynamic analysis respectively. (From ETABS)

Fig. 2. Sample acceleration response generated using ETABS for the building (horizontal direction shows time duration and vertical direction shows acceleration)

Input and Output Data. For ANN training peak values of 24 EQGM data taken as input and the corresponding structural design parameters after considering time history analysis using ETABS for the same 24 EQGM taken as output. All the

input and output data shown in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively. First, we need to convert the EQGM file format to peak values of acceleration, velocity and displacement. Then we will get all the peak values of PGA, PGV and PGD. For the ANN training the peak values of PGA, PGV, PGD and time duration taken as input.

Table 1. Input Data (Peak values of EQGM data and time duration of EQGM)

Sl. No.	Earthquake Name	PGA (g)	PGV (cm/sec)	PGD (cm)	Time Duration(sec)
1	Borrego Mtn	0.133	19.85	14.6	79.98
2	CAPEMEND_FOR	0.106	19.60	29.04	43.98
3	CAPEMEND_SHL	0.229	6.461	0.388	35.98
4	CHICHI.03_TCU115	0.053	15.86	12.07	74.995
5	COALINGA	0.118	23.52	6.881	59.98
6	CORINTH_COR	0.237	22.95	5.720	41.31
7	DUZCE_362	0.026	5.950	8.082	43.15
8	RSN23_SANFRAN_GGP	0.086	2.628	0.070	39.72
9	RSN24_CTRCALIF_B-HCH	0.028	2.158	0.429	76.705
10	RSN25_NCALIF.AG_B-FRN	0.077	3.845	0.810	82.29
11	RSN26_HOLLISTR_B-HCH	0.059	8.011	2.771	40.455
12	RSN27_HOLLISTR_C-HCH	0.056	5.764	1.07	87.61
13	RSN41_LYTLECR_ORR	0.015	0.652	0.085	16.01
14	DUZCE_1061	0.119	12.13	8.775	42.32
15	IWATE_56362	0.145	39.96	21.60	61.99
16	RSN3_HUMBOLT_FRN	0.032	2.363	0.346	39.995
17	RSN4_IMPVAL.BG_B	0.013	0.550	0.054	30
18	RSN5_NWCALIF.AB_A-FRN	0.150	6.122	0.491	39.995
19	RSN10_IMPVAL.BG_C-ELC	0.030	2.727	0.434	39.995
20	RSN11_NWCALIF.AB_B-FRN	0.108	4.659	0.544	39.995
21	RSN16_NCALIF.AG_A-FRN	0.055	6.423	1.034	57.97
22	RSN18_IMPVAL.BG_G-ELC	0.007	0.442	0.051	19.995
23	RSN19_CTRCALIF_A-HCH	0.042	4.101	0.499	57.38
24	RSN21_IMPVAL.BG_E-ELC	0.051	3.722	0.686	39.995
25	iwaTE_55461	0.160	27.39	9.035	59.99

The output data are taken after the Non-linear dynamic analysis (Time History Analysis). Maximum value of each structural design parameter is taken. Maximum value of displacement, story drift, base shear, overturning moment, shear force at Column 1 and bending moment at Column 1 for each EQGM after time history analysis shown in Table 2. Column 1 defined where the x, y and z coordinate shows in Fig. 1. (b) and (c). For each Time history analysis for different EQGM data we got the maximum shear force and bending moment from the column 1 which shown in Table 2.

Artificial Neural Network

ANNs are a type of machine learning that can learn patterns and relationships between variables. They are modeled after the human brain and are composed of interconnected processing nodes, or neurons. A feed-forward multilayer neural network with one hidden layer having 8 neurons used in this paper for ANN training as well as testing. The Levenberg-Marquardt method is employed in this paper to minimize error [16]. All ANN applications were performed using the MATLAB Neural Network Toolbox [17]. For ANN training Sl. No. 1 to 24 from Table 1 and 2 taken as input and output respectively. After training the ANN model, the comparison of structural design parameter from ETABS and ANN model takes place for the last EQGM (sl. No. 25 in Table 1). Incorporating ANNs in seismic retrofitting or structural design in diverse geological settings can offer valuable insights and improve the accuracy of predictions. However, careful consideration of data quality, model limitations, and ongoing validation efforts are crucial for the successful application of ANN models in seismic engineering.

Table 2 Output Data (Structural design parameter after Non-linear Dynamic analysis from ETABS)

Sl. No.	Earthquake Name	Displacement (mm)	Story Drift	Base Shear (kN)	Overturning Moment (kN-m)	Shear Force C1 (kN)	Bending Moment C1 (kN-m)
1	Borrego Mtn	1.717	0.00027	56.37	308.28	13.09	33.896
2	CAPEMEND_F OR	2.324	0.00031	69.41	383.06	17.11	44.654
3	CAPEMEND_S HL	8.054	0.00119	229.72	1291	59.70	155.58
4	CHICHI.03_TC U115	1.05	0.00015	26.79	148.40	7.928	20.564
5	COALINGA	2.173	0.00032	58.68	317.4	16.47	42.692
6	CORINTH_COR	3.906	0.00059	95.22	530.91	30.04	77.6
7	DUZCE_362	0.586	0.00008	15.95	91.335	4.278	11.191
8	RSN23_SANFR AN_GGP	1.671	0.00025	40.37	232.836	12.69	32.884
9	RSN24_CTRCA LIF_B-HCH	0.249	0.00003	6.982	36.97	1.97	5.053
10	RSN25_NCALIF .AG_B-FRN	1.842	0.00027	48.34	275.641	13.87	36.024
11	RSN26_HOLLIS TR_B-HCH	1.561	0.00024	48.83	272.248	11.56	30.126
12	RSN27_HOLLIS TR_C-HCH	1.166	0.00018	36.91	201.974	8.797	22.83
13	RSN41_LYTLE CR_ORR	0.488	0.00007	14.96	84.1826	3.620	9.431
14	DUZCE_1061	3.209	0.00047	92.02	509.274	23.84	62.103
15	IWATE_56362	2.446	0.00036	73.48	407.251	17.62	46.255
16	RSN3_HUMBO LT_FRN	0.956	0.00014	19.81	113.66	7.138	18.568
17	RSN4_IMPVAL L.BG_B	3.328	0.00050	100.5	562.95	24.18	64.024
18	RSN5_NWCALI F.AB_A-FRN	0.566	0.00008	15.68	88.684	4.179	10.896
19	RSN10_IMPVA LL.BG_C-ELC	0.687	0.00010	17.82	100.456	5.005	13.099
20	RSN11_NWCAL IF.AB_B-FRN	3.297	0.00049	97.05	544.044	24.51	63.835
21	RSN16_NCALIF .AG_A-FRN	1.603	0.00023	37.52	212.392	11.88	30.974
22	RSN18_IMPVA LL.BG_G-ELC	0.105	0.00001	3.314	18.6092	0.788	2.033
23	RSN19_CTRCA LIF_A-HCH	1.083	0.00017	35.17	197.356	8.117	21.098
24	RSN21_IMPVA LL.BG_E-ELC	1.227	0.00018	30.43	173.223	9.182	23.851
25	iwaTE_55461	3.735	0.00056	83.25	468.947	28.48	73.727

Results and Discussions

After completion of training of ANN model using the input and output data, the testing of another EQGM name as iwaTE_55461 takes place. We have the input data for the EQGM iwaTE_55461 and after Time History Analysis using the EQGM (iwaTE_55461) we have the structural design parameter in Table 2 sl. No. 25. Now we have to compare the result from ETABS and ANN modelling. By writing the simple code in MATLAB using trained network and the new input value (for EQGM iwaTE_55461) we got the Output structural design parameter for efficient EQ resistant RC frame structure shown in the Table 3. In this research 3 structural design parameter compared such as Storey drift, Base shear and Overturning moment from ETABS and ANN model for the same earthquake ground motion data.

Fig. 3. Neural Network diagram (8 neurons)

Fig.

Algorithms used in ANN model

4.

Fig. 5. Regression Plot of trained ANN model

The developed ANN model and the predicted result for design has been compared with modern and advanced EQ resistant design method viz. THA. The performance of the model is found efficient and consumes considerably less computational time.

Table 3. Structural design parameter from ETABS and ANN model.

	Storey Drift	Base Shear (kN)	Overtuning Moment (kN-m)
From ETABS	0.00056	83.253	468.947
From ANN	0.000706	84.520	470.866

Fig. 6. Comparison of structural design parameter from ETABS and ANN model.

Conclusion

The outcome of the study is found to be promising as Metaheuristic ANN model can be deployed for checking the design parameter without performing detail physical model analysis in a different EQ zone. Following the concept presented in the paper we can save lot of effort and money. The important conclusions on the aforesaid study are appended below,

- When we analyzed the Time History Analysis in Finite Element Software (ETABS) using different EQ ground motion data, we noticed time consuming process. The Finite Element software taking so much time, to overcome this problem we have developed a robust ANN model which can Predict the design parameter of the RC building.
- As we compared the output data from ANN model and Finite Element Software (ETABS) shown in Table 3., the base shear and overturning moment are approximately matching.
- Trained ANN model predicted the structural design parameter of EQ resistant RC building in 0.5 second where the Finite Element software (ETABS) spent 2 minutes for analyzing the RC building for the same EQGM name as iwaTE_55461 (shown in Table1 and 2).
- The developed ANN model is efficient as it can predict design parameters in very lesser time than the computation done by FEM (ETABS). Therefore, the outcome of this paper can be used for design and future research effectively. For future work we may take other input data such as frequency of EQGM, damping ratio and dimension of building etc. for training of ANN model for better result. We may go for different algorithm for ANN training mentioned in Neural Network Toolbox [17].
- The present model works with satisfactory results for data limitations in respect to earthquake ground motion and building. Same model can be made more efficient and general with more data.

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